

Speculation on Quantum Spin, Intrinsic Force and Special Relativity Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 6, 2026

In Part 1, we tried to understand why spin arises. The basic conclusion was that it is linked with an intrinsic force which in turn is associated with E, p (energy momentum) and geometry (rotational symmetry and other symmetries). In practical terms, this means finding an equation linear in intrinsic force (as force appears linearly in nature), but still tied to E, p and geometry. Interestingly, this leads to two very different results for particles with rest mass (spin $\frac{1}{2}$) and photons, although both satisfy the same special relativistic equations (albeit the photon with rest mass $m_0=0$) and both have $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ free wavefunctions.

In the photon case, the Electric field E is the intrinsic force (together with the magnetic B) which gives rise to both energy and momentum density. Specifically, energy density = $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 B \cdot B$ and momentum density = $\frac{1}{c} E \times B$. In the photon case, however, there is no rest frame and so the classical vector E is directly associated with E (energy) and p (momentum) without one needing to consider special relativity. Instead one directly uses Maxwell's electromagnetic equations in order to find a linear equation describing the classical vector E . This equation involves d/dt partial and grad partial which are linked to the quantum operators for E and p ($i\partial/\partial t$, $-i\text{grad}$) and E itself is proportional on $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (actually $\cos(-\omega t+kx)$), also from Maxwell's equations. Given this scenario, one has a classical vector E which is perpendicular to B and both lie in a plane perpendicular to motion. For circular polarization, E moves in a circle and given that it gives rise to energy, this energy circulates like classical angular momentum. For the 3-vector for E , one says that one has spin 1, but for circular polarized light, this is classical angular momentum. As a result, spin in the photon case follows from the behaviour of the intrinsic force (a linear equation in this force as shown in Part 1), but one must also have a clear link between the intrinsic force and the consequential energy and force, because it is the energy which actually has to rotate. It is not enough to have E rotate.

In the case of a particle with rest mass, we argued in Part 1 that m_0 (Newton's inertia) is the intrinsic force which together with velocity gives rise to the consequential energy E and momentum p . The situation is that one actually has two physical frames, the rest frame with the intrinsic force m_0 and the moving frame in which one has E, p . In order to link the intrinsic force m_0 to E, p , one must use a Lorentz invariant. We suggested in Part 1 that $-Et+px = -m_0 c^2 t^2 + (p=0) * (dx \rightarrow \infty) = 0$. Then $dx = \hbar/p$, $dt = \hbar/E$ and E/dx and p/dt are average forces as is $m_0 c^2/dt$. The idea of force is very much the cornerstone of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ we argue. In order to see spin arise, one needs an equation linear in m_0 (the intrinsic force), but linked to E, p and showing geometrical invariances, according to the recipe of Part 1. $-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4$ links E, p, m_0 and shows invariances, but is not linear in m_0 . One must then linearize it. This means that one compares to Lorentz frames, the rest frame containing m_0 and the moving containing E, p . Both m_0 and p are linked to forces, but m_0 is the intrinsic force and p , the consequential. As a result, they must somehow be separated as they are in (γ) , in particular they are perpendicular if one considers: $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1, p \rightarrow px$). In order to linearize without using unit vectors, one cannot use numbers, but must use matrices (as Dirac showed). The operator linked with p_x must anticommute with

that linked with m_0 . The operators associated with the consequential and intrinsic forces differ and in fact anticommute in the rest mass case. One may show that one requires at least a 2×2 matrix (the full Dirac treatment uses a 4-vector made of 2 spinors), which means that there is a two vector state. This is presumably associated with motion, if $\exp(ipz)$ is linked to motion as well.

In order to analyze this 2 vector state (spinor), we first compare the situation with the photon case. There, one had a 3-vector E_i which means that one knows an exact position in the plane. The second piece of information must be the direction in which this vector is moving in a circle (for circularly polarized light). There are two a priori given pieces of information which together with the link between E_i and energy density yields classical angular motion.

In the rest mass case, one again expects rotational motion in a plane perpendicular to the z axis (because p_z describes all motion along z). $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$, however, describe classical rotational direction, clockwise and counterclockwise, but this spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case cannot be classical rotation because the physical vector in the plane is not given (as it is by E_i the intrinsic force). Thus, one has only the direction of rotation. We argue that if $\exp(ipx)$ means that one has p hits at different x within \hbar/p with probability $\exp(ipx)$, one may imagine different x,y positions of energy in the plane (with probabilities) as long as the rotation for $(1,0)$ for each is in the clockwise direction (for example). This means that a physical vector may appear at some x,y in the plane and then at an x_1,t_1 which would be considered a classical time in the past as long as the motion is clockwise. In this way, one may have an angle of 720 degrees (instead of 360 degrees) describe the motion. In terms of interaction with a B field, one has the clear two directions (spin up clockwise and spin down counterclockwise as examples).

Thus, spin must exist in the rest mass case, because one must have m_0 perpendicular to p if special relativity is to hold. If one does not want to have spin, then one must disregard the equivalence of frames moving at constant speeds with respect to each other and that seems unphysical. (Note: There are spin 0 objects (Higgs particle), but we do not consider that here.

The Case of the Photon

Interestingly (as pointed out in Part 1), the photon follows from classical descriptions of Maxwell's electromagnetic equations without sources. The intrinsic force is the classical electric field E_i (which is clearly a classical force in electromagnetic theory). This intrinsic force gives rise to energy and momentum densities:

$$\text{Energy density} = .5\epsilon_0 E_i \text{ dot } E_i + .5/\mu_0 B \text{ dot } B \quad (B=\text{magnetic field}) \quad ((2))$$

We call energy and momentum consequential forces which are created by the intrinsic force E_i (with B). For the case of a photon, there is no rest mass and rest frame versus a moving frame and so E_i , p and E are on the same footing. In fact, one may write a standard wave-equation for E_i and B from Maxwell's em equations and find that E_i behaves as $\cos(-\omega t + px)$. Given knowledge of special relativity and free particle quantum mechanics one may consider this as $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ in order to have Lorentz invariance. E_i and B are perpendicular to each other and lie in a plane perpendicular to motion. If one has a circularly polarized E_i , then this classical vector rotates and given that it is associated with energy, this energy moves like classical

angular momentum. The dynamical behaviour of the intrinsic force immediately gives rise to a physical picture of spin as angular momentum in the circularly polarized case.

In Part 1, we showed that one may formally analyze this by finding an equation linear in the intrinsic force which is linked to invariance in space and p and E . It is this linear equation which shows how EI moves because it is EI which creates the angular motion. In other words, EI is a usual 3-vector in space and so one has the position of energy as well as its rotational direction, i.e. the two basic ingredients to have classical angular motion.

The situation with a particle with rest mass is very different because the rest mass is the intrinsic force and it is not a vector showing position in a plane. Thus, this key piece of knowing the position of the rotating energy is not known for a particle with rest mass and if there is rotational motion linked with the intrinsic force, it should be very different.

The Case of a Particle with Rest Mass

Even though a photon and a particle with rest mass obey the same equations of special relativity (the photon has $m_0=0$), they have very different intrinsic forces (EI electric field in the photon case and m_0 in the particle case). As a result, very different linear equations linking the intrinsic force to E and p and invariances must exist. For example, $E=pc$ holds for a photon from special relativity ($m_0=0$ in $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0$), but the intrinsic force is not present. For a particle with rest mass, this equation displays the intrinsic force m_0 and so may be linearized. This means that in the rest mass case, one must have a Lorentz invariance equation which links to different frames (the rest frame with m_0 and the moving frame with E, p). Physically, one needs a linear equation in the intrinsic force because forces appear linearly in nature. This means that one is forced to linearize $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0$ (as Dirac did). If one linearizes:

$$EE = p \cdot p + m_0 m_0 \quad ((3))$$

Then in the simpler 1-D case one has:

$$E + p \times \text{Matrix 1} + \text{Matrix 2} m_0 \quad ((4))$$

One requires matrices because they must anticommute (as Dirac noted) in order to keep the intrinsic force, m_0 , "perpendicular" to the consequential one. The simplest matrix that may satisfy ((4)) is a 2x2 one, i.e.

$$\text{Matrix 1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Matrix 2} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

Dirac's theory uses 4x4 matrices, and 4 vectors, but there are really two sets of 2x2 matrices and two spinors.

The point is that for a 2x2 matrix, one must have corresponding eigenvectors (1,0) and (0,1). The question is: What do these mean physically?

Given that $\exp(-ipz)$ represents motion in the z direction and the photon has motion in the z direction and rotational motion in a plane perpendicular to z (i.e. x,y), then we suggest that $(1,0)$ means clockwise rotation in the $x-y$ plane and $(0,1)$, counterclockwise rotation. The fundamental problem is that one has not vector in the $x-y$ plane denoting the position of the rotating energy. We argue that this cannot be usual rotation, but must still be rotation in one direction at all times. To accommodate this viewpoint, we consider $\exp(ipx)$ which means that $x=vt$ for the center-of-mass, but that one has probabilistic p hits at different x points given by $\exp(ipx)$. In the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case, we suggest different probability x,y vectors in the $x-y$ plane, each rotating in the same direction for $(1,0)$. This means that for a given x,y vector, the next probabilistic one could be behind it in time (for classical rotation). All one needs is to have it rotate in a clockwise direction with the same strength, but its position may fluctuate just as x fluctuates in $\exp(ipx)$. This could then require sampling 720 degrees to complete a cycle even if one always has rotation in the same direction. It is just that the vector pointing to the rotational energy piece keeps fluctuating about. A B field would detect strength of rotation and direction and would not be bothered by the 720 degrees (as is experimentally the case it seems).

If one believes in that physical equations should be the same in frames moving at constant speed with respect to each other and that force (namely intrinsic force) appears linearly in nature (i.e. rest mass appears as m_0 not m_{momo}), then one should be able to linearize $-E\dot{E} + \dot{p} \cdot p = -m_0 \dot{m}_0$ to obtain an equation linear in the intrinsic force m_0 , but still linked to p, E and invariance. This requires introducing 2×2 matrices and so there must be a 2-state (spinor) which implies a kind of stochastic rotation in one direction for $(1,0)$ as described above. One cannot have special relativity and the notion of linear intrinsic force (rest mass m_0 inertia) without the existence of this probabilistic rotation called spin $1/2$., we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that physically a particle/photon is characterized by its intrinsic force and that it is this force which gives rise to the notion of spin. For the case of a photon, the intrinsic force is the electric field E (together with the B field) and for a particle with rest mass, it is m_0 , the rest mass inertia. Both a photon and a particle with rest mass have E, p and so satisfy the same relativistic equations ($m_0=0$ for a photon) and both have the same quantum $\exp(-Et+ipx)$, but there is still the question of the intrinsic force.

The intrinsic force characterizes a particle and is very different for a photon and rest mass particle. We argue that this intrinsic force is linked with the consequential E and p (i.e. helps to create them). Physically, there should be an equation linear in the intrinsic force (because forces appear linearly in nature) and linked to E, p and invariances. In the case of the E , the electric field for a photon, one may use Maxwell's em equations to find an equation linear in E . One may also show from Maxwell's equations that E is proportional to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (actually $\cos(-i\omega t+ikx)$) and B as well. One may show that a circularly polarized E moves like classical angular momentum in an $x-y$ plane perpendicular to the motion of the photon. Thus, spin here is actually classical angular momentum (circularly polarized light).

In the case of a particle with rest mass, m_0 is the intrinsic force and it does not give a location in an $x-y$ plane. If rotation is to arise, there will be no vector pointing to energy pieces that rotate, so this rotation will be very different, if in fact it exists.

Linearizing $-E\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0 c^2$ to obtain an equation linear in the intrinsic force yields in the simplest case: $\mathbf{E} = \text{matrix 1 } p_z + \text{matrix 2 } m_0$. One cannot have numbers instead of matrix 1 and matrix 2 because one requires anticommutation to keep m_0 and p_z perpendicular and preserve special relativity. We show that one requires at least a 2×2 matrix suggesting eigenstate of $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$. If one assumes that these are linked to rotation in an x - y plane as p_z is motion in the z direction, then $(1,0)$ represents clockwise motion (example) and $(0,1)$ counterclockwise, but there is no position vector pointing to a piece of energy/mass like in the E electric field case. This implies that one may have stochastic rotation, just as $\exp(ip_x)$ is stochastic in x . The x, y vector in the x - y plane is always rotating in the clockwise direction for $(1,0)$, but "jumps" about and so 720 degrees and not 360 degrees seems to be covered. From the point of view of a B field, it sees rotation of a certain strength in a certain direction.